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Mini-Review Article

Classification Of Different Antibiotics And Their Adverse Effects And Uses From Origin To Present

A.L. T. Kalyani*¹, M. S. V. Maha Lakshmi², N. Ahalya³, P. Anusha⁴, S. D. Seema⁵, T. Maneesha⁶

¹Department of Biotechnology, NRI College of pharmacy, pothavarappadu, agiripalli-521212

^{2, 3, 4, 5, 6} Student NRI College of pharmacy, pothavarappadu, agiripalli-521212

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ABSTRACT

Antibiotics are essential in humans 'lives and in animals 'lives. Antibiotic molecules generated by diverse microorganisms have existed for a long time before humans recognized their utility in preventing and treating bacterial diseases. The different types of antibiotics are developed for most of the infections caused by bacteria, fungi, and some microorganisms. Pharmaceutical companies started mass-producing antibiotics in the 20th century; they were mostly synthetic chemicals, but there were also some fully synthetic antibiotic molecules. The development is increased excessively. Due to bacterial resistance strains and isolates, the new drugs for multidrug resistance were improved. Based on antibiotics chemical structures and spectrum of activity the antibiotics were discovered. The different antibiotic shows different mechanism of actions. These antibiotic drugs having side effects or adverse effects, and these can be determined in several pharmacological and clinical studies. To overcome the side effects, the antibiotics are used along with combinations of other drug. The present study in about the classification of different antibiotics and their adverse effects and uses.

INTRODUCTION

The phrase antibiotic—literally "opposing life," derived from the Greek root's anti, "against," and o bios, "Life"—is used generically to refer to any drug used to combat bacteria. Bacteria, viruses, fungus, and parasites are examples of microorganisms, sometimes known as microbes

[1]. Antimicrobials are pharmaceuticals that kill or inhibit the growth of living microorganisms. Examples include:

- Antibacterials (also known as antibiotics and used to treat bacterial infections).

*Corresponding Author: A. L.T. Kalyani

Address: Department of Biotechnology, NRI College of pharmacy, pothavarappadu, agiripalli-521212

Email ✉: kalyani.lakshmitripura@gmail.com

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- Antimycobacterial medicines (antibacterials used to treat tuberculosis and other mycobacterial illnesses).
- Antivirals (active against viral infections such as influenza, HIV, and herpes infections).
- Antifungals (active against fungal diseases).
- Antiparasitic (active against malaria and other parasitic infections) [2].

DIFFERENT CLASS OF ANTIBIOTICS-OVERVIEW

Figure 1: Different classes of antibiotics-an overview

Antibiotic drugs are widely utilized in the treatment and prevention of bacterial infections since they are the most significant form of antibacterial agent [2,3]. They could either kill or hinder the growth of germs. Antibiotics (such as penicillin) are those that are made naturally (by one microbe fighting another), whereas non-antibiotic antibacterials (such as sulphonamides and antiseptics) are completely synthetic. Both groups, however, have the same purpose of killing or blocking the growth of germs, and both are used in antimicrobial chemotherapy. "Antibacterials" include antiseptic medications, antibacterial soaps, and chemical disinfectants, whereas antibiotics are a specialized type of antibacterials used in medicine [4,5] and occasionally in cattle feed. Some new bacterial and fungal strains are often discovered through soil and water samples [6]. An interesting property common to most potent

antibiotics that are very low at concentration they act as growth stimulants [7]. Actinomycetes are the major class which produces about 75% of antibiotics. Streptomyces are the species that makes 75% of all actinomycetes secondary metabolite [8,9,10]. More than 10,000 compounds are isolated from different actinomycetes species where 34% are from streptomyces and 11% are from rare actions [11]. Antimicrobials are currently widely used medications not only in medicine but also in agriculture, cattle farming, and fish farming as growth promoters or growth inhibitors [12, 13]. For some decades, humanity has been free of the threat of catastrophic pandemics [such as plague and syphilis], and diseases such as tuberculosis have been properly treated. Antibiotics gradually gained acceptance among the public as a medical panacea [14].

SCOPE

Antibiotics' clinical usage was undoubtedly the biggest medical breakthrough of the twentieth century [15]. Antibiotics, in addition to treating of these useful drugs, on the other hand, has resulted in a rapid development in antimicrobial resistance (AMR), with some illnesses being effectively untreatable [16]. The hazards of a post-antibiotic era have prompted legislators to

infectious infections, enabled many modern medical treatments, such as cancer treatment, organ transplants, and open-heart surgery. Misuse recognize this threat to human health and pledge greater grant funding, resulting in a gradual rebirth of interest in antibiotic research and development [17]

Figure 2: %n*/year

According to the UK Government-commissioned O'Neill report, without immediate action, 10 million people will die from drug-resistant illnesses each year by 2025. One of the key recommendations is to stimulate early-stage drug discovery [18]. Given the relative lack of success in bringing effective synthetic antibiotics to the

clinic [19]. Filamentous actinomycetes make 64% of the known NP antibiotic classes with the remainder made by other bacteria and fungi. Here we give a brief overview of the history of NP antibiotics and our prospects for discovering, developing, and safeguarding a new generation of antibiotics [20].

Figure 3: Total small molecules/year

HISTORY

Prior to the early twentieth century, infection therapies were mostly dependent on medicinal folklore. Antimicrobial-property mixtures used in infection treatment were described over 2,000 years ago [21]. To treat infections, several ancient cultures, including the ancient Egyptians and Greeks, used specifically selected mold and plant components [22,23]. Tetracycline was discovered in substantial amounts in Nubian mummies investigated in the 1990s. The beer brewed at the time was thought to be the source [24]. Antibiotics were first used in modern medicine with the discovery of synthetic antibiotics derived from dye [25,26]. This marked the beginning of the antibacterial era, which began in 1907 with the discovery of a series of arsenic-derived synthetic antibiotics by both Alfred Bertheim and Ehrlich [27,28].

Figure 4: Arspenamine structure

Arspenamine, also known as salvarsan, discovered in 1907 by Paul Ehrlich. Ehrlich and Bertheim had been experimenting with dye-derived compounds to treat trypanosomiasis in mice and spirochaete infection in rabbits. While their first compounds were too poisonous, Ehrlich and Sahachiro Hata, a Japanese bacteriologist who collaborated with Erlich on the search for a syphilis drug, succeeded with the 606th compound in their series of trials. Ehrlich and Hata revealed their finding, which they dubbed medication "606," at the Congress for Internal Medicine in Wiesbaden in 1910 [29].

PENCILLINS AND OTHER NATURAL ANTIBIOTICS

Observations about the growth of some microorganisms inhibiting the growth of other microorganisms have been reported since the late 19th century. These observations of antibiotics between microorganisms led to the discovery of natural antibacterials. Louis Pasteur observed, "if we could intervene in the antagonism observed between some bacteria, it would offer perhaps the greatest hopes for therapeutics" [30]. In 1874, physician Sir William Roberts noted that cultures of the mould *Penicillium glaucum* that is used in the making of some types of blue cheese did not display bacterial contamination [31]. In 1876, physicist John Tyndall also contributed to this field. In 1895, Italian physician Vincenzo Tiberio presented a paper on the antibacterial properties of mould extracts [32]. Doctoral student Ernest Duchesne submitted a dissertation titled "Contribution à l'étude de la concurrence Vitale chez les micro-organismes: antagonisme entre les moisissures et les microbes" (Contribution to the study of vital competition in microorganisms: antagonism between moulds and microbes) in 1897, the first known scholarly work to consider the therapeutic capabilities of moulds resulting from their anti-microbial activity). Duchesne suggested in his thesis that bacteria and moulds are always fighting for survival. Duchesne discovered that when *E. coli* and *Penicillium glaucum* were cultivated in the when they were both grown in the same culture. He also observed that when he inoculated laboratory animals with lethal doses of typhoid bacilli together with *Penicillium glaucum*, the animals did not contract typhoid. Duchesne's army service after getting his degree prevented him from doing any further research. Duchesne died of tuberculosis, a disease now treated by antibiotics [33]. Sir Alexander Fleming proposed the presence of penicillin in 1928, a chemical produced by certain moulds that kills or inhibits the growth of certain types of bacteria. Fleming was working on a culture of pathogenic bacteria

when he discovered spores of a green mould, *Penicillium rubens* [34], in one of his culture plates. He discovered that the presence of mould either killed or hindered the growth of germs [35]. In 1928, Fleming proposed that the mould secreted an antibiotic chemical, which he termed penicillin. Fleming thought its antimicrobial characteristics could be used in chemotherapy. He originally defined some of its biological features and attempted to treat several infections with a crude preparation, but he was unable to pursue its further development without funding the aid of trained chemist [36].

Figure 5: Florey and chain

1945: Florey and Chain mass produce penicillin. Picking up the torch of Fleming Howard Florey and Ernst chain began testing penicillin on mice and after successful tests they began to create larger amounts for human testing. Although Ernst Chain, Howard Florey, and Edward Abraham were successful in refining the first penicillin, penicillin G, in 1942, it was not generally available outside of the Allied military until 1945. Later, Norman Heatley invented the back extraction technique for bulk penicillin purification. Abraham suggested the molecular composition of penicillin in 1942 [37], and Dorothy Crowfoot Hodgkin validated it in 1945. Purified penicillin was found to have high antibacterial activity against a wide spectrum of microorganisms while being low in toxicity in

humans. Furthermore, unlike synthetic sulphonamide's, its efficacy was not affected by biological elements such as pus. (See note below) The discovery of penicillin rekindled interest in the quest for antibiotic molecules with comparable potency and safety [38]. For their effective growth Chain and Florey shared the 1945 Nobel Prize in Medicine with Fleming for unintentionally discovering but failing to develop as a medicinal medication [39].

particularly efficient in treating wounds and ulcers [40]. Gramicidin, on the other hand, could not be utilised systemically due to toxicity. Tyrocidine was likewise found to be too toxic for systemic

Figure 6: Alexander Fleming

René Dubos was credited with pioneering the strategy of purposefully and systematically searching for antibacterial chemicals, which led to the discovery of gramicidin and revitalised Florey's penicillin research. Dubos announced the discovery of the first naturally produced antibiotic, tyrothricin, a combination of 20% gramicidin and 80% tyrocidine, from *Bacillus brevis* in 1939, coinciding with the commencement of World War II. During World War II, it was one of the first commercially made antibiotics and was

use. During World War II, research results obtained during that period were not shared between the Axis and the Allied nations limited actions to cold war [41]

CLASSIFICATION OF ANTIBIOTICS

Figure 7: Molecular targets of antibiotics on the bacteria cell

Figure 8: Protein synthesis inhibitors (antibiotics)

Antibiotics are often categorised according to their mode of action, chemical structure, or activity spectrum. The majority are directed towards bacterial functions or growth mechanisms. Bactericidal agents are those that target the bacterial cell wall (penicillin's and cephalosporins) or the cell membrane (polymyxins), or that interfere with important bacterial enzymes (rifamycin's, lipiarmycin's, quinolones, and sulphonamides). Except for bactericidal aminoglycosides, protein synthesis inhibitors (macrolides, lincosamides, and tetracyclines) are usually bacteriostatic, limiting future growth [42]. Their target specificity is used

to further categorise them. "Narrow spectrum" antibiotics are those that target certain types of bacteria, such as gram-negative or gram-positive bacteria, whereas broad-spectrum antibiotics are those that impact a wide range of microorganisms. Following a 40-year hiatus in the discovery of antibacterial compound classes, four new antibiotic classes were introduced to clinical use in the late 2000s and early 2010s: cyclic lipopeptides (such as daptomycin), glycylcyclines (such as tigecycline), oxazolidinones (such as linezolid), and lipiarmycin's (such as fidaxomicin) [43, 44]. **BASED UPON NATURE ANTIBIOTICS ARE DIVIDED INTO THREE TYPES:**

NATURAL ANTIBIOTICS:

Natural antibiotics are those which have the property that harm or kill the certain bacteria, viral or other fungal infections.

- Food that kills infection is considered natural antibiotics.
- Natural antibiotics treatments may come with fewer side effects, but also address the infection.
- Natural antibiotics are not synthesized in a laboratory like most antibiotic medication commonly prescribed by the doctors.

It includes examples like.

- TURMERIC
- NEEM
- HONEY
- GARLIC
- ONION
- ECHINACEA
- PENCILLINS
- POLYMXINS
- AMINOGLYCOSIDES
- FUSIDIC ACID

SYNTHETIC ANTIBIOTICS

These are like that of natural antibiotics and these synthetic antibiotics are with the development of antimicrobials, microorganisms have adapted and became resistance to previous antimicrobial agents. For example, penicillium.

Synthetic antibiotics able to synthesize as chemical substance in the laboratory to be used against harmful microorganisms in our environment.

It includes examples like.

- PENCILLIN-V, PENCILLIN-G
- It is the germs that colonise and sometimes infect humans and animals that develop antibiotic resistance, not the humans or animals themselves. Humans and animals do not develop antibiotic resistance, but bacteria and other microorganisms.

- NITROFURANS
- SULPHONAMIDES
- COTRIMOXAZOLE
- OXACILLIN
- AMPICILLIN
- NAFCILLIN

SEMI SYNTHETIC ANTIBIOTICS

1. Antibiotics that contain an original chemical molecule from a microorganism but are further altered are called as semi synthetic antibiotics.
2. The approach of improving on naturally occurring antibiotics carried less risk as the target, selectively and toxicity of the starting antibiotics.

It includes examples like.

- CLINDAMYCIN
- CEPHALOSPORINS
- PLEUROMUTILINS
- AMPHENICOL
- AMINOGLYCOSIDES
- APOMORPHINE
- METHICILLIN
- ERYTHROMYCIN
- TETRACYCLINE

ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE

The ability of a microorganism (e.g., a bacterium, a virus, or a parasite, such as the malaria parasite) to resist the action of an antimicrobial agent is referred to as antimicrobial resistance.

It is a microorganism's response to its surroundings.

- Any antimicrobial treatment drives bacteria to adapt or die.
- Antimicrobial resistance reduces or eliminates the antimicrobial agent's ability to cure or prevent infection caused by bacteria.
- Antibiotic resistance refers to bacteria's ability to withstand the effect of an antibiotic.

- Antibiotic resistance occurs when certain antibiotics lose their ability to kill or inhibit bacterial growth.
- Some bacteria are resistant to particular drugs by nature (intrinsic or inherent resistance).
- A more concerning issue arises when bacteria that are typically susceptible to antibiotics become resistant because of genetic mutation (acquired resistance).
- Furthermore, within a human organism, the genes coding for antibiotic resistance in one type of bacteria can easily spread to other bacterial species via genetic material interchange.
- All resistant bacteria are picked in the ongoing battle for "ecological space" as the antibiotic kills the still-susceptible bacteria around them.
- In the presence of the antibiotic, all antibiotic-resistant bacteria live and continue to grow and reproduce, resulting in prolonged disease or even death.
- Infections produced by antibiotic-resistant bacteria may necessitate further care as well as other, more expensive medications with potentially severe side effects.
- Treatment of antibiotic-resistant bacteria may also necessitate intravenous antibiotics administered in hospitals rather than oral antibiotics administered at home.
- Antibiotic-resistant bacteria can spread once established in a person, and high antibiotic consumption in a population encourages such spread.

Figure 9: A CDC infographic on how antibiotic happens and spreads.

(A major type of antimicrobial resistance)

A microorganism's tolerance to various antimicrobials is referred to as multidrug resistance. This issue of multidrug resistance affects all microorganisms, including bacteria that cause healthcare-associated infections, microorganisms that cause food and waterborne infections, tuberculosis, and microorganisms that cause sexually transmitted diseases such as

gonorrhoea and HIV. The problem with multidrug-resistant germs is that there are few (if any) choices for treating people infected with these pathogens.

Examples of common multidrug-resistant bacteria are:

- Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA)
- Vancomycin-resistant enterococci (VRE)
- Extended-spectrum beta-lactamase

(ESBL)-producing Enterobacteriaceae (examples of common Enterobacteriaceae are *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*) Multidrug-resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* *Clostridium difficile*.

- The two primary causes of antibiotic resistance are:
- Antimicrobial use places ecological strain on microorganisms and leads to the formation and selection of antimicrobial-resistant bacteria in populations.
- Antimicrobial-resistant microbe spread and cross-transmission between humans, animals, and humans and animals in the environment.
- As a result, the two key areas for antimicrobial resistance management, control, and prevention are:
- Antimicrobial prudence (using antimicrobials only, when necessary, at the precise dose intervals, and for the correct period); Hand hygiene, screening, isolation, and other hygienic procedures for the control of antimicrobial-resistant microorganism cross-transmission (infection control).
- Antimicrobials used in food-producing animals contribute to a portion of the EU's antimicrobial resistance burden. Because antibiotics used to treat and prevent illnesses in animals belong to the same chemical groups as those used in human medicine, animals may harbour germs resistant to antibiotics used to treat diseases in humans.
- Certain bacteria, such as *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*, are linked to contaminated meals and cause diarrhoea.
- Even when antibiotics are used correctly, bacteria can acquire antibiotic resistance as a natural adaptive response. Infection control precautions are required whenever antibiotic-resistant bacteria appear and grow to prevent
- Animals may carry antimicrobial-resistant *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* that are passed from animals to humans through food; humans may also acquire antimicrobial-resistant bacteria through direct contact with animals, as is the case with certain MRSA strains isolated from livestock, particularly pigs.
- However, the most common cause of antimicrobial resistance in human microorganisms is the use of antimicrobials in human medicine, the community, hospitals, and other healthcare settings.
- At individual/patient level.
- Antibiotics inevitably alter the natural bacterial ecology of humans, resulting in side effects such as diarrhoea, as well as the appearance and/or selection of antibiotic-resistant bacteria.
- These resistant bacteria can live for up to six months and perhaps longer without producing infection.
- Patients who are colonised by/carry resistant germs are more likely to become infected with these resistant bacteria than with susceptible forms of the same bacteria.
- Antibiotics should not be administered when they are unnecessary, such as for viral diseases like common colds or influenza.
- When antibiotics are required (a decision made by a medical doctor who writes a prescription), they must be used correctly, i.e., at the correct dose, at the correct intervals, and for the prescribed duration, to maximise effectiveness in curing the infection and minimising the emergence of resistance. spread from carriers of infected patients to other patients or person [2].

DIFFERENT TYPES OF ANTIBIOTICS

TABLE 1: ANTIBIOTICS ACCORDING TO THEIR YEARWISE INVENTION:

IT INCLUDES:

- Different Types Of Antibiotic Drugs
- Discovered In The Year
- Which Source It Is Obtained From
- Which Microorganism It Is Isolated From
- Scientist
- In Which Year The Drug Clinically Approved.

Sr. NO	DRUG	DISCOVERED IN THE YEAR	SOURCE	MICRO ORGANISM/CHEMICAL NAME	SCIENTIST	CLINICALLY APPROVED
1	Penicillin	1928	Fungi	Penicillium chrysogenum	Alexander flemming	1943
2	Sulfonamides	1932	Prontosil	Mafenide	Gerhard domagk	1936
3	Bacitracin	1943	Bacteria	Bacillus subtilis	Balbine johnson	1948
4	Aminoglycosides	1944	Actinomycetes	Streptomyces kanamycetius	Selman waksman	1946
5	Nitrofurantoin	ss1945	Nitrofurantoin	Nitrofurantoin	Kenyon j.hayes	1953
6	Amphenicol	1947	Chloromycetin	Streptomyces venezulae	Mildred c.rebstock	1949
7	Cephalosporin	1948	Bacteria	Acremonium chrysogenum	Giuseppe brotzu	1964
8	Pleuromutilins	1951	Fungus	Pleurotus mutilus	Pleuromutilin	1979
9	Vancomycin	1955	Soil bacteria	Amycolatopis-orientalis	Mack H.mcormick	1958
10	Colistin	1958	Bacteria	Bacillus polymixa	Y.koyama	1959
11	Metronidazole	1960	Anaerobic bacteria	Nitrating 2-methyl-imidazole	Rhone-poulenc	2005
12	Fusidic acid	1960	Fungi	Acremonium fusidioides	Leopharma in baller up	1962
13	Nalidixic acid	1962	Bacteria	Choloroquine synthesis [1,8-naphthyridine]	George lesher	1964
14	Tobramycin	1965	Aminoglycoside	Streptomyces tenebrius	Selman waksman's	1975
15	Clindamycin	1966	Lincomycin	Streptomyces lincolnensis	Braney.J. magerlein, Robert D	1968
16	Fidaxomicin	1970	Actinomycete dactylopragium	Clostridium difficile	Joanna giles, April roberts	2011
17	Cefaclor	1973	Fungus	Chloro-2-amino-2-phenyl acetamide	Eli lilly and co	1979
18	Mupirocin	1976	Bacteria	Pseudomonas fluorescens	Suthern landetal	1986
19	Salbutam	1977	Beta lactamase	Ecoli	Richard roxburgh	1986
20	Ofloxacin	1979	Aerobic bacteria	4-quinolone	Daiichiseiyaku	1980

21	Clarithromycin	1980	Erythromycin	Staphylococcus aureus	Taishoph	1990
22	Azithromycin	1980	Erythromycin	Staphylococcus aureus	Slobodin dokic	1988
23	Telavancin	2000	Bacteria	Vancomycin	Leadbetter, M.R. et al.	2009
24	Bedaquiline	2004	Bacteria	Mycobacterium tuberculosis	Jassen	2012
25	Ceftaroline	2010	Fungus	Streptococcus SPP	Takeda	2010

PENICILLINS

Penicillin's are discovered by Alexander Fleming in the year 1928. It is obtained from fungi which is isolated from *Penicillium chrysogenum*. It was clinically approved in the year 1943.

MECHANISM OF ACTION:

The peptidoglycan cell wall that envelops the bacterial plasma membrane in the majority of bacteria maintains structural integrity and inhibits osmotic lysis. Replication and growth involve constant remodelling of the peptidoglycan wall. Penicillin prevents peptidoglycan in the cell wall from cross-linking [45]. Penicillin-binding proteins, such as the enzyme DD-transpeptidase, act as a catalyst for this process. DD-transpeptidase can bind to the four-membered β -lactam ring of penicillin, rendering it irreversibly inert. When a result, even when other proteins keep rupturing the wall, the bacteria are unable to form new ones [46]. Osmotic pressure causes water to enter the bacterium cell and destroy it when the cell wall weakens further. Because peptidoglycan fragments can activate hydrolases and autolysins, they further damage the cell wall [47].

ADMINISTRATION:

- It is possible to administer penicillin G intravenously or intramuscularly.
- Penicillin V and penicillin VK, which is the potassium salt of penicillin V, can be taken orally [48].

ADVERSE EFFECTS:

Hypersensitivity:

Immediate onset: Twenty minutes after administration is when this type of reaction happens. Urticaria, pruritis, oedema, laryngospasm, bronchospasm, hypotension, vascular collapse, and mortality are its defining features. Delayed onset: This reaction happens one to two weeks after starting therapy. Fever, malaise, urticaria, myalgia, arthralgia, abdominal pain, and skin rashes are some of its uncommon symptoms [49].

• Gastro intestine system:

GI symptoms, which include nausea, vomiting, and stomatitis and are frequently seen with oral treatment, were the most prevalent and were recorded in more than 1% of patients. It is also noted that pseudomembranous colitis occurs during or following treatment.

• Metabolic reactions:

When given IV in large doses, the salt form of penicillin G may produce electrolyte abnormalities, i.e., hyperkalemia [50].

CONTRAINDICATIONS:

Penicillin contraindications include a history of severe adverse responses to penicillin or its derivatives. Penicillin is also not recommended for patients who have developed Stevens-Johnson syndrome after receiving penicillin or a penicillin derivative. Because penicillin exist in low concentrations in breastmilk, they are safe to use during pregnancy and nursing. Penicillin has an antagonistic impact with tetracycline and is said to increase the risk of mortality by 2.6 times while

treating pneumococcal meningitis than penicillin alone [51].

USES:

- It is used to treat throat infection.
- It is used to treat meningitis.
- It is used to treat syphilis.

BACITRACIN

Bacitracin is discovered by Balbina Johnson in the year 1943. It is obtained from bacteria and is isolated from *Bacillus subtilis*. It is clinically approved in the year 1948.

MECHANISM OF ACTION:

Bacitracin is a combination of three closely related cyclic polypeptide antibiotics that have both bacteriostatic and bactericidal characteristics depending on medication concentration and microorganism susceptibility. Bacitracin quickly absorbs through denuded, burnt, or granulated skin and helps to block mucopeptide transfer into the cell walls of many microbes. This affects bacterial cell wall synthesis and, eventually, bacterial multiplication. Bacitracin also inhibits proteases and other enzymes involved in bacterial cell membrane function. Bacitracin prevents the dephosphorylation of the P-P-phospholipid carrier that links the cell wall peptidoglycan precursor units to the cell membrane, resulting in bacterial cell lysis [52].

ADMINISTRATION:

Bacitracin is available in three forms in the United States: topical, ophthalmic, and parenteral by intramuscular injection. Its most typical application is as a topical treatment applied directly to the wound or diseased region. It can also be used to treat superficial ocular infections of the conjunctiva and cornea as a topical ophthalmic ointment in a formulation specifically designed for ocular usage [53].

ADVERSE EFFECTS:

- Common and Minor Adverse Effects
- Fever
- Hives

- Itching
- Lip and facial swelling [54]
- Having trouble breathing
- Nausea
- Vomiting [55]

CONTRAINDICATIONS:

- Anyone who is allergic to bacitracin or any of its medication formulation components should avoid using topical bacitracin. Patients who have a known neomycin hypersensitivity may also be sensitive to bacitracin.
- Bacitracin administration to an illness or wound caused by a viral or fungal infection may increase the probability of drug-resistant bacteria developing [56].

USES:

- It is used to treat acute and chronic localized skin infections
- It is used to treat minor skin injuries

AMINOGLYCOSIDES

Aminoglycosides are discovered by Selman Waksman in the year 1944. It is obtained from *Actinomycetes*. It is isolated from *Streptomyces kanamycetus*. It was clinically approved in the year 1944.

MECHANISM OF ACTION :

Aminoglycosides have bactericidal effect against "most gram-negative aerobic and facultative anaerobic bacilli" but not against gram-negative anaerobes or most gram-positive bacteria [57]. Protein synthesis is inhibited by aminoglycosides' energy-dependent, and sometimes irreversible, binding to the cytosolic, membrane-associated bacterial ribosome. The presence of aminoglycosides in the cytosol often disrupts peptide elongation at the 30S ribosomal subunit, resulting in erroneous mRNA translation and hence production of proteins that are truncated or have changed amino acid compositions at specific locations [58]. In particular, binding hampers translational proofreading, resulting in RNA

message misinterpretation, premature termination, or both, and thus inaccuracy of the translated protein product. It has been proposed that aminoglycoside antibiotics cause guanine nucleotide oxidation in the bacterial nucleotide pool, which adds to their cytotoxicity. Because inadequate repair of closely spaced 8-oxo-2'-deoxyguanosine in the DNA might result in deadly double-strand breaks, insertion of oxidized guanine nucleotides into DNA could be bactericidal [59]. Finally, an additional "cell-membrane effect" occurs with aminoglycosides; "functional integrity of the bacterial cell membrane" might be lost later in aminoglycoside exposure and transit time periods [60].

ADMINISTRATION:

They are injected intravenously and intramuscularly since they are not absorbed through the digestive tract. A few are utilized in topical wound treatments. For gut purification (e.g., in hepatic encephalopathy), oral dosing is an option. Nebulized tobramycin is a possible dosage form [61].

ADVERSE EFFECT:

- Aminoglycosides have the potential to produce inner ear poisoning, which can lead to sensorineural hearing loss [62].
- Frequent usage of aminoglycosides may cause kidney damage (acute renal injury), which may progress to chronic kidney disease [63].

CONTRAINDICATIONS:

- Aminoglycosides can aggravate weakness in persons with myasthenia gravis, hence they should be avoided [64].
- Aminoglycosides are not recommended for patients with mitochondrial disorders because they can disrupt DNA translation, resulting in irreversible hearing loss, tinnitus, cardiac toxicity, and renal toxicity. Hearing loss and tinnitus have been found in some patients who do not have mitochondrial illness [65].

USES:

- It is used to treat urinary tract infections.
- It is used to treat pneumonia.
- It is used to treat urinary renal tract infections.

NITROFURANS

Nitrofurans are discovered by Kenyon J. Hayes, in the year 1945. It is obtained from nitrofurantoin. It is obtained from nitrofurantoin. It was clinically approved in the year 1953.

MECHANISM OF ACTION:

Nitrofurantoin exerts antibacterial activity through a variety of methods. Bacterial intracellular flavoproteins absorb nitrofurantoin and convert it to reactive intermediates. This reduction produces intermediate metabolites that bind to bacterial ribosomes and block bacterial enzymes involved in the synthesis of DNA, RNA, cell wall protein synthesis, and other metabolic enzymes [66].

ADMINISTRATION:

Nitrofurantoin is only available as an oral medication [67].

ADVERSE EFFECTS:

- Nausea, vomiting, appetite loss, and diarrhea are the adverse medication reactions that are more frequently reported.
- Pulmonary toxicity is the most well-known severe reaction [68].

CONTRAINDICATIONS:

The medication should not be used in women who are 38 to 42 weeks pregnant, during labor and delivery, or when labor is about to begin. It should also not be given to newborns who are less than a month old. This is due to the potential for immature erythrocyte enzyme systems, notably glutathione instability, to induce hemolytic anemia. Since prostatitis is frequently associated with urinary tract infections, nitrofurantoin should not be administered to men who have these infections since it is ineffective at penetrating prostatic tissue [69].

USES

- It is used to treat urinary tract infection.

- It is used as a topical antimicrobial in wound management.
- It is used to treat infections from susceptible bacteria such as *E. coli*, staphylococcus aureus, streptococcus pyogenes and *Aerobacter aerogenes*

AMPHENICOL

Amphenicol are discovered by Mildred C.Rebstock in the year 1947.It is obtained from synthesized active chloromycetin is isolated from streptomyces venezulae. It is clinically obtained in the year 1949.

MECHANISM OF ACTIONS:

Chloramphenicol inhibits the synthesis of proteins by attaching itself to the 50S ribosomal subunit and obstructing the production of bacterial proteins [70]. Chloramphenicol prevents transfer RNA from attaching to the 50S ribosome's a site at the molecular level.

ADMINISTRATION:

Chloramphenicol can be administered topically as eye or ear drops, or as an eye ointment. It can also be given parenterally as intravenous injection or infusion or taken as oral capsules.

ADVERSE EFFECTS:

Aplastic anemia has been known to be fatally caused by chloramphenicol; taking it with cimetidine may increase this risk [71].

CONTRAINDICATIONS:

The use of chloramphenicol is strictly prohibited in patients with acute porphyria [72]. Furthermore, the use of alternative antimicrobials should be justified in cases with known hypersensitivity to chloramphenicol, such as prior anaphylactic reactions to the medication. Anaphylactic reactions to the drug can manifest as urticaria, bronchospasm, and edema[73]. There have also been reports of delayed onset hypersensitivity responses, including contact dermatitis. This reaction frequently manifests as edema and erythema 24 to 72 hours after the drug is applied [74].

USES:

- It is used to treat eye infections.
- It is used to treat otitis externa.
- It is used in the treatment of typhoid.

CEPHALOSPORIN

Cephalosporin discovered by Giuseppe Brotzu in the year 1948.It is obtained from bacteria and isolated from *Acremonium chrysogenum*. It is clinically approved in the year 1964.

MECHANISM OF ACTION:

Penicillin-binding proteins (PBP, peptidoglycan transpeptidase) crosslink peptidoglycan units to strengthen the cell wall that bacteria manufacture. Beta-lactam rings are the mechanism of action for cephalosporins, a broad class of bactericidal antimicrobials that were first produced from the fungus *Cephalosporium* species. The penicillin-binding protein is bound by the beta-lactam rings, which prevent it from functioning normally. When bacteria are unable to produce a cell wall, they perish.

ADMINISTRATION:

First generation:

Parenterally given cefazolin, cephalothin, and cephapirin. Both cefadroxil and cephalexin are administered orally. Parenteral or oral cephradine administration is possible.

Second-generation:

Oral or parenteral administration of cefuroxime is possible. The administration of cefprozil is oral. Parenterally administered cefoxitin, cefotetan, and cefmetazole are used.

Third-generation:

Cefotaxime, ceftazidime, and ceftriaxone administration is via the parenteral route. Cefdinir, cefixime, and cefpodoxime are administered orally [75].

Fourth generation:

Parenteral administration of cefepime is used. Parenterally administered ceftaroline is considered fifth-generation.

ADVERSE EFFECTS:

Disulfiram like -Reaction:

Acetaldehyde can build up as a result of the aldehyde dehydrogenase enzyme being inhibited by cephalosporins with a methyltetraazolethiol side chain. Cefamandole, cefoperazone, and moxalactam are the cephalosporins that cause this reaction the most frequently [76].

Insufficiency of Vitamin k :

Vitamin K epoxide reductase can be inhibited by several cephalosporins, which stops the synthesis of reduced (active) vitamin K. The patient is therefore at risk for hypoprothrombinemia due to a reduced production of coagulation factors [77].

False Membranous Coli:

Clindamycin and ampicillin usage are frequently linked to pseudomembranous colitis. Another prominent cause of pseudomembranous colitis is the use of cephalosporins, particularly third-generation cephalosporins [78].

CONTRAINDICATIONS:

Due to reports that ceftriaxone displaces bilirubin from albumin, raising free bilirubin concentrations and raising the risk of jaundice in newborns, it is contraindicated in neonates with hyperbilirubinemia. Ceftriaxone interacts with a calcium-containing solution and can precipitate in newborns under 28 days old's kidneys and lungs, which can be fatal. Consequently, if a newborn under 28 days old is anticipated to get any calcium-containing goods, ceftriaxone should likewise not be administered to them [79].

USES:

- It is used to treat pneumonia.
- It is used to treat sinuses.
- It is used to treat the lung infections.

VANCOMYCIN

Vancomycin is discovered by Mack H.Mcormick in the year 1955. It is obtained from soil bacteria and isolated from *Amycolatopsis orientalis*. It is clinically approved in the year 1958.

MECHANISM OF ACTION:

Components to Vancomycin are an antibiotic that is based on glycopeptides. It works by preventing the bacterial cell wall's peptidoglycans from polymerizing [80]. The bacterial cell wall is made up of a rigid layer of peptidoglycan that is composed of long polymers of N-acetylglucosamine (NAG) and N-acetylmuramic acid (NAM) that are highly cross-linked. By binding to D-alanyl D-alanine, vancomycin inhibits the P-phospholipid carrier and glucosyltransferase (peptidoglycan synthase), which stops NAM and NAG from being synthesized and polymerized within the peptidoglycan layer. Bacterial cell death results from this inhibition, which erodes the bacterial cell walls and eventually allows intracellular leak out [81]. The exclusive target of vancomycin is gram-positive bacteria.

ADMINISTRATIONS:

Vancomycin may be taken orally or via intravenous injection, according to FDA approval. Vancomycin can be used off-label to treat *Clostridium difficile* infections through rectal administration. The kind and location of the infection determine how it should be administered. Because of its low oral bioavailability, vancomycin is typically administered intravenously to treat infections [82].

ADVERSE EFFECTS:

Intravenous vancomycin injection side effects frequently include hypersensitivity reactions, hypotension, and nephrotoxicity [83]. One kind of hypersensitivity reaction that vancomycin can cause is anaphylaxis [84].

Rapid intravenous infusion of vancomycin is linked to an infusion-related reaction called vancomycin flushing syndrome (VFS), formerly known as redman syndrome. Flushing, itching, and an erythematous rash on the face, neck, and upper torso are among the symptoms.

CONTRAINDICATIONS:

- **Clinical Points to Remember:**

Vancomycin does not have many contraindications, however there are a few crucial clinical factors to be aware of when providing care for patients.

- **Resistance of Bacteria:**

Similar to other antimicrobials, extended or unsuitable vancomycin treatment can result in the development of bacterial resistance, including vancomycin-resistant enterococci (VRE) [85].

USES:

- It is used to treat colitis that may occur after antibiotic treatment.
- It is used to treat an infection of intestines caused by *Clostridium difficile*, which can cause bloody diarrhoea.
- It is used in infections caused by multiple drug resistance bacteria.

METRONIDAZOLE

Metronidazole is discovered by Rhone-poulenc in the year 1960. It is obtained from anaerobic bacteria, and it is isolated from nitrating 2-methylimidazole. And it is clinically approved in the year 2005.

MECHANISM OF ACTION:

When metronidazole interacts with DNA, it causes strand breaks and a loss of helical DNA shape in addition to diffusing throughout the body and inhibiting protein production. As a result, it results in cell death in species that are vulnerable.

There are four steps involved in the metronidazole mechanism of action. The first step is the pathogen's admission into the organism through diffusion through the anaerobic and aerobic cell membranes. However, only anaerobes have antibacterial properties [86]. Pyruvate-ferredoxin oxidoreductase's molecular structure is changed in step two by intracellular transport proteins, resulting in reductive activation. Metronidazole reduction produces a concentration gradient in the cell that encourages the uptake of more medicines and the production of cytotoxic free radicals [87].

Interactions with intracellular targets, the third step, are accomplished by cytotoxic particles engaging with the DNA of the host cell, breaking DNA strands and fatally destabilizing the DNA helix. The degradation of cytotoxic compounds is step four [88]. Although the exact mechanism of action of metronidazole against facultatively anaerobic bacteria such as *Helicobacter pylori* and *Gardnerella vaginalis* is unknown, it is cytotoxic to these pathogens.

ADMINISTRATION:

An oral, intravenous, or topical administration is available for metronidazole. It can be applied topically, intravenously, as a pill or tablet [89].

ADVERSE EFFECTS:

The drug metronidazole has a black box warning that suggests it can cause cancer in mice and rats, according to certain animal studies. Long-term drug usage carries a danger of cumulative neurotoxicity, which can lead to serious neurological problems [90].

CONTRAINDICATIONS:

In addition to being contraindicated in patients with a history of drug or component hypersensitivity, metronidazole should not be used during the first trimester of pregnancy. In addition, patients should abstain from alcohol and propylene glycol-containing goods for three days after finishing their metronidazole treatment. Additionally, if disulfiram has been used during the last two weeks, metronidazole should not be administered [86].

USES:

- It is used to treat Rosacea and mouth infection.
- It is used to treat the dental abscesses.

TOBRAMYCIN

Tobramycin is discovered by Selman Waksman in the year 1965. It is obtained from aminoglycosides and it is isolated from *Streptomyces tenebrarius*. It was clinically approved in the year 1975.

MECHANISM OF ACTION:

The bacterial 30s ribosomal unit's 16s ribosomal RNA component binds to tobramycin, preventing translation from starting [91]. Tobramycin binds to the A-site, where it causes mistranslation and misreading of the codon by transfer RNA, which results in the erroneous delivery of aminoacyl units. Because of the way that incorrectly generated proteins accumulate inside the cell and cause disruptions to the cell membrane and numerous cellular functions, tobramycin is classified as a bactericidal agent [92].

ADMINISTRATION:

- Tobramycin can be used topically, intravenously, intramuscularly, or inhaled. Because to the poor bioavailability caused by the efflux P-glycoprotein pump in the intestinal brush barrier, oral dosing is not recommended [93].
- To treat ocular infections, clinicians can use tobramycin as a 0.3% ophthalmic solution or 0.3% ointment [94].
- Pneumonia linked with cystic fibrosis can be treated with oral tobramycin inhalation [95].
- Serious bacterial infections have been treated using intramuscular injection, intravenous infusion, and intraventricular (off-label) treatment [96].

ADVERSE EFFECTS:

The rRNA's general structure is conserved in many species, but aminoglycosides have a much stronger affinity roughly ten times for the rRNA of prokaryotes than eukaryotes. The tobramycin adverse effect profile cannot be adequately explained by this increased binding affinity. The most frequent side effects include headache, nausea, skin rash, dizziness, and confusion. Tobramycin can cause ototoxicity, neuropathy, and nephrotoxicity, which are serious adverse drug reactions. There have been a few documented rare cases of tobramycin-related liver damage [97].

COTRAINDICATIONS:

Patients who are hypersensitive to tobramycin or any other aminoglycoside antibiotics are considered contraindications. Elderly patients, people who are easily dehydrated, and people who already have medical conditions such as renal failure, neuromuscular disorders like myasthenia gravis, or Parkinson's disease should also use caution [98].

USES:

It is used to treat the blepharitis.

It is used to treat conjunctivitis

CLINDAMYCIN

Clindamycin is discovered by Braney J.Magerlein, Roberts D in the year 1966. It is obtained from Lincomycin. It is isolated from *Streptomyces lincolnensis*. It was clinically approved in the year 1968.

MECHANISM OF ACTION:

Clindamycin binds to 50S ribosomal subunits reversibly and inhibits the formation of peptide bonds, which in turn inhibits the synthesis of proteins. Clindamycin can be either a bacteriostatic or bactericidal antibiotic, depending on the organism, infection site, and drug concentration [99].

ADMINISTRATION:

Clindamycin can enter the body through a variety of methods. It can be applied topically to treat acne vulgaris as a foam, gel, lotion, or solution. It is necessary to apply a thin film twice daily. It is available as a cream and suppository for intravaginal administration to treat bacterial vaginosis [100].

ADVERSE EFFECTS:

The way that clindamycin is administered affects its side effects differently. When topical medication is used, pruritis, xeroderma, erythema, burning, exfoliation, or oily skin is the most frequently reported side effects. The most typical adverse reactions to intravaginal medication include vulvovaginal disease, vulvovaginal candidiasis, pruritis, and vulvovaginitis.

Clindamycin primarily causes pseudomembranous colitis, nausea, vomiting, and diarrhea when administered systemically. This is because clindamycin destroys a large portion of the healthy flora in the GI tract [101].

CONTRAINDICATIONS:

Patients with a history of ulcerative colitis or pseudomembranous colitis should not take clindamycin. When using antibiotics, caution is also required because superinfections with bacteria and fungi can happen. Additionally, it should not be administered to individuals who are allergic to clindamycin, lincomycin, or any of their constituents [102].

USES:

- It is used to treat the intra-abdominal infections.
- It is used in Lower respiratory infections.
- It is used in treatment of Gynaecological infections

CONCLUSION

There is a need of antibiotics in our life. Some antibiotics are discovered from natural, synthetic, and semi synthetic sources. Different classes of antibiotics are discovered and the use of antibiotics in treatment is essential in modern medicines. The antibiotics misuse causes serious threat to public health. The invention of antibiotics is done to overcome the resistance of antibiotics towards bacteria, fungi, and microorganisms. For genetic disorders, there are no antibiotics. But the research is going on, for the discovery of new antibiotics towards genetic diseases. Further research is going on for the autoimmune diseases and genetic related diseases.

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